

EVALUATION OF QUALITY ASSURANCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL EDUCATION IN PONOROGO REGENCY

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Abstract

Quality assurance of national education is carried out to educate the nation's life and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation through the SNP. The principle is to encourage managers, administrators, and education units to improve their performance in providing quality educational services and software to encourage transparency and public accountability. In its implementation, education quality assurance policies must adapt to changes and developments in science and technology and rapid global dynamics. The quality of Indonesian education has not been as expected. Accreditation to BAN-S/M, the development of school quality has not shown an encouraging development in the quality of education. The factor is not that the SNP is of low quality but that the fulfillment and implementation of the SNP have not been running optimally. The objective of this research is to: 1) Describe and analyze the evaluation of quality assurance policies for primary school education in Ponorogo; 2) Examine the factors that encourage and obstruct education quality assurance.; 3) look at the quality and functional education quality assurance model. This research uses a qualitative descriptive research method. The data analysis technique used was evaluation. Data were analyzed interactively. Single Program Before After evaluation model with the type of ongoing evaluation (ongoing/concurrent evaluation) carried out when the program is implemented. The criteria for evaluating public policies used are effectiveness, efficiency, evaluation, equity, responsiveness, and accuracy. The results of the study: 1) The quality assurance of elementary school education in Ponorogo has not reached the SNP because there is a reduction in information in the SPMI induction system through the school model. 2) The implementation of education quality assurance in all elementary schools, the commitment to achieve the SNP, and the availability of data-based documents, are supporting factors for quality assurance. The occurrence of a reduction in information has an impact on the availability and ability of resources, quality audits have not worked according to their duties and functions, not all schools have used education quality reports in the preparation of school work plans, and assistance from school supervisors is less than optimal; 3) The education quality assurance model needs to be emphasized on the Span of Control, namely direct subordinates can be led and controlled effectively by a manager, because of human limitations, namely limited time, knowledge, abilities, and attention.

Keywords: *Evaluation, Quality, School.*

A. Introduction

As mandated by Law (UU) Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, article 5 states that Every citizen has the same right to obtain a quality education. Furthermore, based on article 11 paragraph (1), it is explained that the Government and Local governments are obliged to provide services and facilities and ensure the implementation of quality education for every citizen without discrimination. In realizing quality education, the

government issued Government Regulation (PP) Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards (SNP) and its amendments, that every education unit on formal and non formal channels is required to carry out quality assurance of education. The quality assurance of education aims to meet or exceed the SNP. This can be realized if schools whose entire ecosystem has a collective awareness to encourage a continuous, continuous, and continuous process of achievement and quality improvement. The SNP in question includes graduate competency standards, content standards, process standards, educational assessment standards, educators and education personnel, standards for facilities and infrastructure, education management standards, and financing standards.

Quality education does not happen by itself but results from an educational process that runs well, effectively, and efficiently. As a conformance requirement, the quality is following the standards that have been required. A product or service is of high quality when following established quality standards, including the quality of inputs, processes, and outputs (Crosby, .1979:58). Crosby's concept of quality is strengthened by Arcaro (2005, 85); quality is a comprehensive description and characteristics of goods or services that show their ability to satisfy expected needs. In the context of education, the notion of quality includes educational inputs, processes, and outputs. According to Pongtuluran (2017), three definitions of quality are distinguished based on hierarchy: quality control, total quality assurance, and quality management. Based on this understanding, there is an equation, namely quality, regarding the degree of conformity with the requirements.

A quality assurance is a series of programs that monitor and evaluate various aspects of a product, project, or service to ensure that each part of a project meets quality standards (Williams and Harvey, 2015). Furthermore, according to Williams, J (2016), quality assurance must be managed from internal and external processes that are highly recognized by procedures that are known to all stakeholders. Continuous quality assurance will encourage the emergence of quality enhancement is a continuous process. Process Quality assurance (PQA) is a program improvement process that, based on the concept of a planned, systematic, and documented continuous improvement cycle, aims to improve the quality of learning and the program's relevance. This opinion aligns with Matovu's (2017) opinion that a quality assurance is a collection of policies, procedures, systems, and practices designed to achieve, maintain and improve education. According to Elassy and Noha (2015), quality assurance and quality improvement are part of the spectrum, where quality improvement depends on quality assurance.

Schools in Indonesia, although the implementation of school quality assurance, formally only started in 2016, namely when the emergence of the guidelines for quality assurance of primary and secondary schools launched by the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary Education of the Ministry of Education and Culture, but in fact, the quality assurance movement had existed long before that. In subsequent developments, the quality assurance movement became faster and faster in primary schools, at a time when all scenarios of block-grant provision must be included to provide quality assurance.

This factor is the factor that most spurs the emergence of quality assurance platforms in Indonesia. In the end, many implementations of quality assurance at the basic education level were born not because of internal encouragement in the form of quality culture but limited to the importance of fulfilling administrative requirements for obtaining block grants.

The phenomenon that occurs in the elementary school level education unit in Ponorogo, including in the education quality mapping (PMP) data collection activity which is a School Self-Evaluation (EDS) activity, filling in PMP instruments is carried out quickly and as long as it is filled in without using valid data. Schools do not understand the purpose and benefits of collecting data, so it does not match the existing reality when the quality report card appears. Even the quality report cards of 2016 and 2019 cannot be read. This is supported by good report cards so far that have not reached the required standard, namely reaching the SNP with a lower limit of 6.67 and an upper limit of 7 or exceeding the SNP.

In the condition that there is still a Covid-19 pandemic which is currently referred to as the New Normal, quality assurance in the education unit must still be carried out, although, of course, it still adjusts to the health protocols that the government has set. This is certainly adjusted to the situation, conditions, and needs.

The government promotes the students' health while still paying attention to their right to quality education. The process of guaranteeing the quality of education in this new normal period will support the smooth running of Distance Learning (PJJ). Therefore, stakeholders must synergize in promoting quality education so that 8 SNPs can be achieved.

Evaluation of the quality assurance policy of primary school education becomes interesting to evaluate. As the education unit with the highest number, elementary schools will have opportunities for coloring education, especially in the Education Office of Ponorogo Regency area. Based on the background, the focus of this research lies in evaluating the quality assurance policy of elementary school education in the Education Office of Ponorogo Regency. The basic education quality assurance policy that will be evaluated is the Minister of Education

and Culture Number 28 of 2016 from quality assurance, supporting and inhibiting factors, and the preparation of an education quality assurance model.

A policy that the government has implemented should need to be evaluated. Evaluation is carried out because not all public policies can obtain policymakers' desired results or impacts.

Policy evaluation, in the perspective of the process flow/cycle of public policy, occupies the last position after the implementation of the policy, so, naturally, the public policy that has been created and implemented is then evaluated. Evaluation is a series of activities in implementing a policy or a program. With the evaluation, an institution's effectiveness, efficiency, quality, performance, or productivity will be known in implementing its programs and improving them. Evaluating educational policies and programs is also inseparable from using concepts and evaluation theories in general, only focusing more on educational content.

Policy Evaluation. Lester and Stewart (2000, in Winarno (2007), in general, policy evaluation can be said as an activity involving the estimation or assessment of policies that include substance, implementation, and impact. Policy evaluation, according to Dunn Dalam Gadjah Mada press (2000), is intended to know four aspects, namely (1) the policy-making process; (2) the implementation process; (3) policy consequences; (4) the effectiveness of policy impacts. Meanwhile, according to Lester and Stewart (1996), policy evaluation can be distinguished into two different tasks: (1) M determines what consequences a policy has by describing its impact. In brief, this task refers to efforts to identify causality or the cause/impact of the policy; (2) Assess the success or failure of a policy based on predetermined criteria.

Policy evaluation studies are descriptive and analytical; on the one hand, evaluation studies seek to describe the impact and results that have been achieved. On the other hand, evaluation studies seek to describe implementing a policy. So, in conducting an evaluation study, there are several types of evaluation studies.

Evaluation of public policy, in the stages of its implementation, uses the development of several indicators to avoid the emergence of bias and as a guideline for evaluators. In this study, using the evaluation criteria according to William N. Dunn quoted Gadjah Mada Press (2003) describes the criteria for public policy evaluation: effectiveness, efficiency, adequacy, equity, responsiveness, and accuracy.

Finsterbusch and Motz in Wibawa (1994) mention four types of program evaluation based on the strength of conclusions: Single program after only, Single program before after, Comparative after only, and Comparative before after. The research on Quality assurance Evaluation of Primary School Education in Ponorogo Regency uses a type of evaluation of a single before-after program.

Education Quality assurance. Development is the most centric thing in almost all countries. Globally, the building has become the moral standard for seeing the progress of a country, with its primary marker lying in the economic sphere. The basis of development is looking at the economic and social aspects, including education. According to Deddy T. Tikson (2005), national development can also be interpreted as a deliberate economic, social, and cultural transformation through policies and strategies toward the desired direction. The significance of development is progress, growth, and diversification (Digdowiseiso, Kumba.2019:9).

The preamble to the 1945 Constitution mandates the state to educate the nation's life. This statement is emphasized in Article 31, paragraph (1), which states that every citizen has the right to be taught. Subsection (2) emphasizes that the government should strive for and implement a national teaching system governed by law. This shows how important education is in Indonesia. Education is part of the direction of Human Resources (HR) development, namely building hardworking human resources who are dynamic, productive, skilled, and mastering science and technology supported by industry cooperation and global talents. The direction of human resource development is one of the 7 (seven) national development agendas for 2020-2024, namely increasing quality and competitive human resources. Improving the quality and competitiveness of human resources is expected to produce the next generation of the nation who are healthy, intelligent, adaptive, innovative, skilled, and have character.

Following the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 22 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2020-2024 focuses on the Merdeka Belajar policy as a guide for hr development in organizing and maximizing demographic bonuses which are the key to achieving a developed nation with social justice, as aspired by the founders of the nation. This can be achieved through quality education.

Quality education does not happen by itself but results from an educational process that runs well, effectively, and efficiently. As a conformance requirement, the quality is following the standards that have been required. The presence of quality assurance has a strategic role in realizing quality education. Quality assurance is a set of programs that monitor and evaluate various aspects of a product, project, or service to ensure that every part of a project meets quality standards (Williams and Harvey, 2015). As Rosa and Amaral (2014) described, quality assurance as a professional and internationally networked activity is faced with global challenges, then quality assurance is also becoming increasingly complex.

Meanwhile, according to Williams and James (2016), Quality assurance must be managed from internal and external processes that are highly controlled by procedures known to all

stakeholders. Continuous quality assurance will encourage the emergence of quality enhancement is a continuous process. Process Quality assurance (PQA) is a program improvement process based on a planned, systematic, and documented continuous improvement cycle to improve the quality of learning and the relevance of the program as a whole. Furthermore, Matovu (2017) defines a quality assurance as a collection of policies, procedures, systems, and practices designed to achieve, maintain and improve the quality of education offered.

According to Pongtuluran (2017), three definitions of quality are distinguished based on hierarchy, namely: quality control, quality assurance, and total quality management.

Following the Minister of Education and Culture No. 28 of 2016, the primary and secondary education quality assurance system consists of the internal quality assurance system (SPMI), implemented in education units by all components of the education unit and the external quality assurance system (SPME) implemented by the government, local governments, accreditation institutions, and educational standardization institutions. The quality assurance information system that supports the implementation of the two systems follows a cycle of activities according to their respective components.

The SPMI cycle consists of quality mapping, preparation of fulfillment plans, implementation of fulfillment plans, evaluation / audit of plan implementation, and determination of quality standards. meanwhile, the external quality assurance system (SPME) cycle consists of (1) Mapping the quality of education units based on National Education Standards; (2) Quality improvement planning as outlined in the strategic plan, and (3) Facilitation of quality fulfillment in all education units, (4) Monitoring and evaluation of the process of implementing quality fulfillment, (5) Determination and evaluation of national education standards, (6) Implementation of accreditation of education units or expertise programs. The information system of quality assurance of primary and secondary school education can be described as follows:

Figure 1: Education Quality assurance information system

Source : Education Quality Indicators Book

The primary and secondary education quality assurance system is a unity of integrated organizations, policies, and processes that regulate all activities to improve the quality of primary and secondary education that interact systematically, planned, and sustainably. The education unit carries out the internal quality assurance system (SPMI) in this connection. SPMI is a unity of elements consisting of policies and processes related to guaranteeing the quality of education carried out by each basic education unit and secondary education unit to ensure the realization of quality education that meets or exceeds the National Education Standards."

The government has rolled out the national standards of education (SNP) as a benchmark for the quality of education. In order to measure the quality of an education unit, it can be seen the suitability between the SNP and the condition of the whole education unit. A request for quality in the forum for quality assurance

of education is needed to ascertain whether the education unit carries out the SNP to improve the quality of education in a systemic, holistic, and sustainable manner to grow and develop a quality culture in education independently. Based on its function, quality assurance is a controller of the implementation of education by the education unit to realize quality education.

B. Methods

This study examines the quality assurance evaluation of elementary schools in Ponorogo Regency. The type of policy evaluation used in the research is the Single Program Before and after because what will be studied is what takes place after the education quality assurance policy, so that information on changes in the target group can be obtained. Meanwhile, the conditions before the policy are implemented are used to compare the conditions after the education quality assurance policy is implemented. This study uses evaluation criteria

according to William N. Dunn, namely: fecundity, efficiency, adequacy, equality, responsiveness, and accuracy.

This research is policy research, which follows the Constructivistic paradigm with a qualitative approach. The methods used are descriptive and focused on policy evaluation. Descriptive research describes the actual state of the object under study and according to the actual state of affairs at the time of direct research. The principle of qualitative research is naturalistic or natural because the research field situation is natural or natural. The data processed in this study is from primary data and secondary data. Primary Data is data obtained directly from the first source through in-depth interviews and observations made by researchers.

Secondary data is data related to a pre-existing event obtained through documents, research reports, articles, related regulations, research results, and other forms that can provide information in research. Data collection techniques use interviews, observations, and documentation—data analysis technique with reduction techniques, display, concluding / verification.

C. Results and Discussion

This study uses James Williams's theory concerning internal and external quality assurance. On this basis, the aspects evaluated are related to (1) National Standards for Education (SNP) as a quality reference; (2) Internal Quality Assurance System (SPMI), (3) External Quality Assurance System (SPME), Fsupporting actors and quality assurance assistance, and Penyusunan quality assurance model that is quality and functional. The policy evaluation criteria used by William N Dunn's theory include effectivity, efficiency, adequacy, equality, responsiveness, and accuracy.

National Standards of Education (SNP). Based on the inter-achievement of interview data and observations that have been carried out, it can be known that some of the findings are related to the National Education Standards (SNP). In general, schools have understood and implemented the objectives of national education and the IP principles of education delivery. This is supported by the enormous commitment and contribution of school residents in realizing national education goals following their respective roles.

The school understands the SNP so that there are various changes in the system and services in education. All schools have run SPMI with the support of the leadership of quality assurance documents. Education authorities have provided socialization, coaching, and monitoring evaluation. The implementation of Education Quality Mapping (PMP) in the

Education Unit is supported by the government through school operational assistance funds, in addition to supporting through the Teacher Working Group (KKG), the principal Working Group (KKS), and the School Supervisory Working Group (KKPS).

Concerning the factor supporting the success of PMP, the school implements the PMP cycle, and the results reflect the portrait of the quality of the school. PMP is a form of School Self-Evaluation (EDS). Based on the observations, the results of the achievement of the SNP were followed up for improvement. Education units report the results of SNP achievements regularly. The standards that are always carried out institutionally by the stem of quality assurance are the Implementation of Graduate Competency Standards, Content Standards, Process Standards, and Assessment Standards. Regarding evaluating PMP obstacles, there are many obstacles to implementing *online* instrument filling so that offline filling is taken first and then uploaded *online*.

The school has also understood the quality report card. Understanding and attributing to the lowest quality report card from TPMPS in the School Operator element (OPS), many OPS have a heavy workload. All administrative management that is currently based on digital becomes OPS's responsibility. There is even an OPS who doubles as the treasurer of the BOS, and there is also an OPS that the homeroom teacher appoints. At the same time, 100% OPS is purely from honorary personnel / wiyata bakti. The principal's digital-based duties are often handed over to the OPS. In the education unit, the OPS is responsible for the database.

The assistance of school superintendents in fulfilling SNP is less than optimal, but school residents are committed to providing quality school services. Currently, the number of academic units with the number of supervisors is not balanced because many supervisors are retired, while the recruitment of supervisors is carried out after problems arise. Many Supervisors have to double tasks between sub districts that have a reasonably long distance. The supervisor must divide the time, as a result of which the assistance from the supervisor is less than optimal. Not all schools have reached SNP. The internal quality audit team is less than optimal in carrying out its duties and functions, and not all schools use EDS as the basis for the preparation of school work plans (RKS). Schools have limitations on the availability of human resources that have a complete understanding of quality assurances. The achievements of the SNP at the Ponorogo Regency elementary school level as a result of mapping the quality of education based on the achievements of the SNP from 2016 to 2020 are presented in Figure 2 as follows: Figure 2: Results of education quality mapping based on SNP achievements in 2016 until 2020.

Internal Quality Assurance System. School residents understand SPMI and respond to government policies related to SPMI based on Permendikbud Number 28 of 2016. All schools have implemented SPMI and have quality report cards. The Regional Facilitators (Fasda) are well versed in the concept and implementation of SPMI.

Regional Facilitators provide guidance and guidance for SPMI regularly outside the LPMP schedule, but not evenly because they focus on model schools and impact schools. Furthermore, the school supervisors and principals were informed that they mastered the concept and implementation of SPMI with various levels of understanding. Principals and school supervisors oversee and provide direction on SPMI directly to the team and school residents and provide support for the SPMI program in fulfilling the SNP. to run it); Supporting facilities (SPMI socialization training, supporting technology).

Regarding the evaluation of the implementation of the SPMI mentoring system in elementary schools, mentoring is often carried out at least once a semester with a minimum mentoring time allocation of 5 (five) days according to the schedule for three years for the target school model and its impact. The allocation of time and stages of assistance can be adjusted to the situation and conditions of each region. The Education Office of Ponorogo Regency, through the TPMPPD, supervises the education unit to find out the existence of TPMPS in implementing the SPMI according to the program, although not regularly.

All schools have documents related to SPMI in the form of TPMPS Team Decree, SPMI Structure and Commitment, SPMI Work Program, SPMI /8 SNP Cycle, and Quality Reports/EDS. Regarding the evaluation of the understanding of the SPMI cycle, all schools have implemented the SPMI, but not all schools have implemented the SPMI according to the cycle. School Self-Evaluation based on the quality report card as the first step in the SPMI cycle has not been carried out. The results of the EDS are the basis for compiling a quality improvement plan with the output of the school work plan. The school has carried out quality compliance based on the plans that have been prepared. The internal quality audit team monitors and evaluates quality compliance, and the results are the basis for determining the new quality.

There are factors inhibiting the success of SPMI, namely: (1) Not all schools have implemented SPMI according to the cycle; (2) Schools have not been able to achieve SNP; (c) Lack of educators and education staff who have a complete and correct understanding of SPMI; (4) the ineffectiveness of SPMI from model schools, because it is still nuanced in fulfilling the requirements for obtaining Block grant funds. This results from the impact system with model schools in a long span, resulting in a reduction in information. School

supervisors in carrying out their roles related to SPMI need to be optimized. Meanwhile, TPMPS has not carried out its functions related to SPMI because the school did not receive direct socialization from the local facilitators. TPMPS plays a strategic role in achieving SNP through SPMI, but not all TPMPS work according to their duties and functions, especially the Internal Quality Audit team. This is because the quality audit team has a heavy workload. The quality audit team members are the teachers at the school who have duties as classroom teachers. Even those who double as treasurers of BOS, extra- curricular coaches, and are in charge of several standards. This is because elementary schools' teaching and educational staff are minimal.

SPMI runs according to standards, while the supporting factors for the successful implementation of SPMI are: (1) SPMI socialization to all school members directly, not through representatives (2) Strong principal leadership; (3) The paradigm shift in the school community is aware of the importance of quality assurance and needs to be continuously fostered and given understanding; (4) Commitment from TPMPS and school members (5) Learning spirit, (6) understanding each stage of SPMI, (7) Consistency in the implementation of SPMI, (8) Optimal guidance from TPMPD through school supervisors.

According to the National Education Standards Achievement Category for Elementary School (SD) Ponorogo Regency, the quality map for elementary school levels is presented in Figure 3 below.

Based on the confirmation of research findings with research criteria, 5 (five) evaluations can meet the six criteria. So only 1 criterion has not been met, namely effectiveness, because the SNP has not been achieved. For the quality assurance of this elementary school to be more effective, it is necessary to carry out a span of control. As explained, the quality assurance theory used in this study uses Williams. J theory (2016),

Also informed is the comparison of quality assurance before and after Permendikbud. Number 28 of 2016, concerning the Education Quality assurance policy. Before being rolled out, the guideline for education units to conduct quality assurances using EDS (School Self-Evaluation) was the implementation of the Education Quality assurance System (SPMP) as regulated in the Minister of National Education Regulation Number 63 of 2009. EDS is a school self-evaluation process internal in nature that involves stakeholders to see school performance based on Minimum Service Standards (SPM) and National Education Standards (SNP), whose results are used as the basis for preparing School Development Plans (RPS) or School Work Plans (RKS) and as input for investment planning education at the district/city level. The school self-evaluation process is a cycle, starting with forming a School

Development Team (TPS), training in instruments, implementing EDS in schools, and using the results as the basis for preparing RPS/RKS and RAPBS/RKAS.

Based on this, the EDS is the school's responsibility to carry out quality assurance concerning the quality of the SPM and SNP. The results of the EDS are not well documented, as is the case with the SPMI quality report cards, which are more accurate, although EDS and SPMI are intended for education quality assurance. EDS is more administrative than SPMI, and the results are less accurate, so many schools are apathetic. So quality assurance based on Permendikbud Number 28 of 2016 is more effective.

External Quality Assurance System. School residents understand the purpose of SPME, according to Permendikbud. No. 28 of 2016, only the level of understanding is different. It is also stated that school principals carry out socialization about the accreditation system in schools. About the primary variable of accreditation according to the mechanism in POS accreditation. The school has complete documents related to accreditation.

While the success factors for implementing SPME through accreditation are supported by several factors, namely, leadership commitment, school management commitment; commitment of each individual who will run this quality system; consistency is always maintained in every activity as well as in making decisions/attitudes and the availability of an accurate database that is used every time a decision is made. The results of the accreditation are mostly following the achievements of the SNP. While those who answered 'no' were schools waiting for the regrouping process to be completed.

The success of accreditation is influenced by leadership, commitment from school leaders and citizens, the availability of accurate data, and available infrastructure; the results of this observation follow the agree and strongly agree to answers from all sources of informants amounting to 100% for each informant source. The results of the evaluation of the results of school accreditation are an assessment of the feasibility of schools based on the aspect of fulfilling the SNP and tend to be administrative; in terms of the utilization of the accreditation, results are still not satisfactory.

The results of the post-accreditation follow-up evaluation carried out by schools make the accreditation results the basis for making decisions in the preparation of steps or policies that will be taken in the next period. Accreditation is one of the considerations for parents when choosing a child's school. Accreditation means acknowledging an educational institution granted by an authorized body after assessing that the institution meets specific standard requirements or criteria.

However, the accreditation assessment can also negatively impact when the school community is only trying to get grades and status/labels. The improvement in the performance of the school component is only limited to when a temporary accreditation will be carried out after completing the accreditation assessment; the school will return to its original state and will only grow enthusiasm when it is accredited.

The results of school accreditation in elementary schools in the area of the Education Office of Ponorogo Regency follow the SNP achievements of SPMI in schools. The accreditation results so that the results accreditation are directly proportional to the achievement of quality report cards. This can be seen from the results of the 2016-2020 re-accreditation as follows:

This can be seen from the results of re-accreditation in 2016-2020 that the accreditation results are grouped by predicate according to the provisions of the classification of accreditation ratings, which can be described that in 2016 there were 126 primary schools institutions targeted for accreditation. The results obtained are 1 C-accredited institution, 97 B-accredited institutions, and 28 A accredited schools. In 2017 there were 96 primary school institutions targeted for accreditation.

The 2017 accreditation results show 6 C-accredited institutions, 83 B-accredited institutions, and 7 A-accredited institutions. Meanwhile, in 2018, there were 96 primary school institutions targeted for accreditation.

The results of the 2018 accreditation showed 6 C-accredited institutions, 83 B accredited institutions, and 7 A-accredited institutions. In 2019 there were 74 primary school institutions targeted for accreditation; the result was one non accredited institution, 22 C-accredited institutions, 60 B-accredited institutions, and 11 A-accredited institutions. While in 2020, there are 13 accreditation target SD institutions, the accreditation results show 10 B-accredited institutions and 3 A accredited institutions.

Supporting Factors and Obstacles to Education Quality Assurance. Factors supporting the success of quality assurance of primary school education in Ponorogo Regency are: (1) Schools have an understanding of the National Education Standards (SNP); (2) All school members contribute to realizing the national education goals in accordance with their respective abilities and roles; (3) Schools are committed to achieving SNP; (4) All schools have implemented SPMI, and have implemented SPME through accreditation activities; (5) All elementary schools have documents related to education quality assurance; (6) Availability of accurate database; (7) The Regional Government through the Education Office provides support for educational units in achieving SNP; (8) All schools have quality report cards; (9) The education

office has TPMPD, regional facilitators, and school supervisors who are committed and consistent in overseeing quality assurance in education units by building effective communication; (10) All schools have TPMPS; (11) There is support for active participation from the community; (12) The Department of Education provides support in the form of granting permission to conduct research on the evaluation of the quality assurance of primary school education in Ponorogo Regency.

The inhibiting factors for ensuring the quality of education are as follows: (1) As many as 99.82% of elementary schools in Ponorogo Regency have not yet reached the SNP; (2) There is information reduction in the implementation of the SPMI inducing system; (3) There is limited availability of human resources who have a complete and correct understanding of SPMI; (4) Not all TPMPS members work optimally according to their duties and functions, especially the internal quality audit team, (5) OPS has a heavy workload; (6) School supervisors in carrying out their role as guarantor of the quality of education in education units are less than optimal; (7) Not all schools have utilized the quality report card in the preparation of the School Work Plan.

Development of Education Quality Assurance Model. The formulation of the quality assurance model for primary school education in Ponorogo Regency departed from research findings related to the factors inhibiting quality assurance success for primary school education in Ponorogo Regency. For five years since the Minister of Education and Culture Number 28 of 2016 was issued, the achievement of quality assurance at the elementary school level in Ponorogo Regency has not been able to reach the SNP. a span of control is required. Aimed at the need for Span of Control. (Span of Control) in the Organization due to limited time, limited knowledge, limited ability, and Limited attention. Thus, according to the researcher, it is necessary to add a Span of Control variable at the level of internal quality assurance.

The following is a functional education quality assurance model proposed by the researcher.

Figure 5. Proposed Model of Education Quality Assurance

Source: Modification of the QA Model William, J

Span of Control serves to guard against information reduction at each stage of internal quality assurance so that quality assurance runs more effectively in achieving SNP and optimizing the role of school supervisors as education quality guarantors. In this model, there is the addition of an element of the span of control so that it becomes Internal, Span of control, External (ISE).

Figure 5 explains that Quality Assurance can be described as a systemic, structured, and continuous concern for quality in terms of quality maintenance and improvement. Quality assurance of a system has two different wings: (1) Internal Quality Assurance (IQA); (2) External Quality Assurance. (Williams, J. 2016). Furthermore, it is also explained that quality assurance must be managed from internal and external processes, which are strictly controlled by procedures known to all stakeholders.

D. Conclusion

Based on the research results on the evaluation of the quality assurance of elementary school education in Ponorogo Regency, it can be concluded as follows: 1) The quality assurance of elementary school education in Ponorogo has not reached the SNP because there is a reduction in information in the SPMI induction system through the school model. 2) The implementation of education quality assurance in all elementary schools, the commitment to achieve the SNP, and the availability of data-based documents, are supporting factors for quality assurance. The occurrence of a reduction in information has an impact on the availability and ability of resources, quality audits have not worked according to their duties and functions, not all schools have used education quality reports in the preparation of school work plans, and assistance from school supervisors is less than optimal; 3) The education quality assurance model needs to be emphasized on the Span of Control, namely direct subordinates can be led and controlled effectively by a manager, because of human limitations, namely limited time, knowledge, abilities, and attention.

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